

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL FAILURE PREDICTIONS OF BIAXIALLY-LOADED UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

The genesis for this study was the desire to produce an accurate assessment of a unidirectional composite's behavior when subjected to a complete biaxial loading interrogation, resulting in a data set which previously did not exist in open literature. Both numerical and experimental approaches are documented and reported.

Keywords: Biaxial Testing, Failure Analysis, Composite Strength, Multicontinuum

INTRODUCTION

Through pioneering efforts such as the World Wide Failure Exercise [1], the greater composites community has recently and profoundly demonstrated the inability to accurately predict the response of composite materials; a limitation which has already, and will continue to, hampered the optimal use of composite materials. One key omission from that effort, as well as the general open literature, is the determination of the biaxial response of unidirectional laminates when subjected to a complete two-dimensional biaxial loading. As a result, a collaborative program between the US Air Force Research Laboratory, CSA Engineering, and Firehole Technologies was initiated to numerically predict and experimentally verify the biaxial strength of unidirectional IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy composite laminates. Numerically, a micro-level approach, MultiContinuum Theory (MCT), was used to predict and analyze the onset of damage and ultimate failure of biaxially loaded cruciform test specimens. These MCT failure predictions were then validated experimentally using a unique triaxial test facility capable of performing both biaxial (two-dimensional, in-plane) and triaxial (three-dimensional) strength measurements.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

In numerous previous studies [2-8], a series of thickness-tapered cruciform specimen configurations have been used to determine the biaxial (two-dimensional, in-plane) and triaxial (three-dimensional) strength of several carbon/epoxy and glass/vinyl-ester laminate configurations. Refinements to the cruciform geometry have led to successful evaluations of the biaxial strength of cross-ply, quasi-isotropic, and woven laminate configurations. However, the order-of-magnitude strength difference between the σ_{11} and σ_{22} directions provides significant challenges when interrogating a unidirectional

laminate. In the present study, a two-dimensional failure envelope for an IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy laminate was generated at the Air Force Research Laboratory, Space Vehicles Directorate, using a triaxial test facility shown in Figure 1A by testing the refined thickness-tapered cruciform specimen shown in Figure 1B [9]. The electromechanical test frame is capable of generating any combination of tensile or compressive stresses in $\sigma_1:\sigma_2:\sigma_3$ stress space and can evaluate the uniaxial (one-dimensional, in-plane), biaxial or triaxial response of composite materials.

Figure 1. A – Triaxial Test Facility at the Air Force Research Laboratory, B – Thickness-Tapered Cruciform Test Specimen.

Regardless of the specific analysis and experiments performed in this study, the authors have spent considerable time and effort characterizing the uniaxial and biaxial response of many IM7/977-2 carbon/epoxy laminates [7-8]. As a result, the unidirectional response of this laminate was already well-known and the experimental portion of the present study began by identifying suitable specimen geometry that would lead to acceptable specimen behavior and failures when failed. Due to space limitations of the current paper, only a brief description of the specific test procedures will be provided; however, the interested reader is referred to the applicable references for additional information regarding the test procedures used [2-4,6-9]. All results presented adopt the composites nomenclature of Hyer [10].

By far, the biggest challenge with performing the biaxial tests in the presents study compared to the previous studies was the simple fact that a unidirectional laminate is not symmetric in the 1-2 plane as all previous biaxial tests performed by the authors have been. While this is presents perhaps the simplest laminate configuration to analyze and manufacture, the dramatic strength and stiffness difference, which for this material system was known to be as much as three orders of magnitude, between the in-plane principal directions of a unidirectional presented many challenges in testing. Primary concerns centered on the ability to physically machine cruciform specimens without damage in the transverse direction and performing load control tests with dramatic stiffness differences between the principal directions. Experimentally, both of these issues increased the probability of premature failure in the uniaxially loaded arms resulting in an invalid test.

Initially, a unidirectional laminate was designed with integrated reinforced tabs on the arms using a $[(90)_6/(0)_6]_S$ laminate configuration. The thickness-tapered cruciform specimens were initially laid-up as flat laminate plates from which the desired cruciform

specimen shape, including gage section, was machined out using a computer numeric controlled (CNC) mill. That is, in physically machining the specimen to the desired thickness, the 90-degree portions of the laminate were removed from the gage section but retained in the loading arms to provide much-needed machining and handling strength and stiffness in the transverse direction in the loading arm area of the thickness-tapered cruciform specimen. Material remaining in the gage section was the desired 8-ply unidirectional laminate to be tested which was driven by the load frames capacity and the strength of the specimen in the 1-direction. Although the load magnitude to fail the coupon in the 2-direction was relatively small, it was believed to be sufficient to garner useful data. A preliminary set of results demonstrated the stress ratios containing compressive loads required a thicker gage section to prevent buckling induced by manufacturing imperfections in the specimen. Compressive failure could be achieved in a thicker cross section due to the material's reduced compressive strength. This ultimately led to the use of two different gage section thicknesses. The previously mentioned specimen was used to test four biaxial stress ratios. Adopting the authors standard biaxial testing nomenclature of x-direction stress/y-direction stress for the present study, the stress ratios evaluated with the 8-ply gage section coupon were 1/0, 5/1, 1/1, and 0/1. The second test article configuration consisted of a $[(90)_{10}/(0)_{10}]_S$ laminate with an 18-ply gage section. It was used to characterize seven stress ratios; -5/1, -1/0, -3/-1 -1/-1, 0/-1, and 5/-1. Two successful tests were conducted for each stress state with the exception of the 1/0 and 0/1 cases, in which three specimens were examined because these data points were needed for comparison with the material's standard uniaxial strengths. This process lends credence to the validity of the biaxial coupon's failure mechanism. Figure 2 represents a photograph of a biaxial test specimen loaded in a -1/-1 stress ratio until ultimate failure. The symmetric failure through the center of the gage section leads the authors to have a considerable amount of confidence that the current experimental test methods are generating accurate failure data, as any other failure surface would indicate sub-optimal test conditions and results.

Figure 2 Thickness-Tapered Cruciform Specimen Failure Surface when Subjected to -1/-1 Loading Conditions.

Due to the uniqueness of the acquired data set, all the specimens in this study were instrumented with either uniaxial or biaxial strain gages to monitor the strain to failure. This is a departure from the authors' standard, and previously published, practice.

Although the strain gage was typically damaged or debonded from the gage section during initial failure of the coupon, the data provided a redundant evaluation of the specimen's stiffness and stress state for a significant portion of the test. Perhaps the greatest difference between this study and biaxial characterizations previously conducted at AFRL is the definition of the reported biaxial strengths. Formerly, the measured biaxial strength of each specimen was defined to be when the test specimen could no longer support any additional load in either in-plane direction. Since the specimen's strength was as much as 40 times greater in the 1-direction versus the 2-direction, the biaxial strength for this study is stress in the x-direction when the specimen was no longer able to support an increased load in the y-direction. In each case the test was continued until the coupon ultimately failed in the x-direction as well, however, the damage caused by ultimate matrix failure, and the overall condition and geometry of the gage section was unknown for that portion of the experiment. The final fiber direction failure is reported for the 5/1 and 1/1 stress cases, however the reasons discussed above yielded insensible results for the remainder of the coupons.

NUMERICAL TECHNIQUES

MultiContinuum Theory (MCT) was used to analytically predict the IM7/977-2 unidirectional failure envelope. MCT incorporates the classical micromechanics based strain-decomposition technique of Hill [11] into a numerical algorithm that extracts the stress and strain fields for a composite's constituents. Thus, MCT retains the basic nature of the composite's constituents (fiber and matrix) in a structural analysis as separate but linked continua so that the responses of these most basic components can be determined at every point in the structure. Failure analysis was performed using Helius:MCT™ and conventional Hashin-based failure criteria as supplied by ABAQUS.

The concept of a multicontinuum simply extends the notion of a continuum to reflect coexisting materials within a material point. Such an extension is natural in any case where there are two, or more, clearly identifiable constituents with drastically different material properties. Given a composite stress and strain field, and assuming linear elastic behavior in an incremental loading scheme, it is a straightforward matter to decompose the composite fields down to their constituent level stress/strain fields for the fiber and the matrix. The specific linear elastic equations applicable to this decomposition may be found in Mayes and Hansen [12].

Simple quadratic stress-based failure criteria (Eqs. 1-2), expressed in terms of transversely isotropic stress invariants of the constituents (Eqs. 3), are used to predict constituent failure within a lamina.

$$\pm A_{1f} I_{1f}^2 + A_{4f} I_{4f} = 1, \quad (1)$$

$$\pm A_{1m} I_{1m}^2 - \pm A_{2m} I_{2m}^2 + A_{3m} I_{3m} + A_{4m} I_{4m} - \pm A_{5m} I_{1m} I_{2m} = 1, \quad (2)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \sigma_{11}, \\ I_2 &= \sigma_{22} + \sigma_{33}, \\ I_3 &= \sigma_{22}^2 + \sigma_{33}^2 + 2\sigma_{23}^2, \\ I_4 &= \sigma_{12}^2 + \sigma_{13}^2. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

In Eqs. 1 and 2, the $I_{i\beta}$ terms denote transversely isotropic stress invariants for each constituent, $\beta=f$ for fiber, $\beta=m$ for matrix. The coefficients A_{if} and A_{im} , leading the invariants, are constituent failure parameters, generally derived from experimentally determined composite ultimate strength data through correlation with the MCT decomposition.

Multicontinuum technology failure analysis of the unidirectional cruciform specimens was performed using two methods. One method uses Helius:Laminate [13] a desktop software application that produces failure envelopes for constant state of stress loadings. It uses classical laminated plate theory to access ply-level stresses and the MCT composites failure simulation technology [14-15] to predict failure in individual constituents. Only the gage section of the cruciform specimen is represented using this method and a constant state of stress is assumed. The entire $\sigma_x:\sigma_y$ biaxial failure envelope generated in this study was generated in under one second.

The second method uses Helius:MCT [16] in conjunction with Abaqus/Standard [17]. This method applies the same MCT composites failure simulation technology as Helius:Laminate to a detailed finite element analysis of the specimen. Local stress distribution through the specimen is captured. Progressive failure is performed on the specimen where failure prediction causes element by element stiffness reduction. The failure data reported represents ultimate failure of the specimen, determined by a discrete change in the global stiffness of the specimen during the progressive failure analysis.

To generate the biaxial failure envelopes presented in the present study, twelve individual finite element analysis at various $\sigma_x:\sigma_y$ load ratios were simulated. Two finite element models were used in the analysis to coincide with the specimens used in the experiment. Both models used a single three dimensional solid element per ply in the gage section and layered solid elements in the arms. The compression specimen model contained 23,856 elements and the tension specimen model contained 19,113 elements, both models are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Finite Element Mesh of the Compression Specimen (Left) and Tension Specimen (Right).

Boundary conditions were applied to create one-eighth symmetry in the models. Loads were applied to a single node on the cut boundary of either arm. Constraint equations were applied to each cut boundary to distribute the load evenly across the arm. The

stress in the gage section was calculated using a simple force/area calculation. Material properties used in the analysis are shown in Table 1. A typical progressive failure analysis contains between 250 and 300 equilibrium iterations and would complete in approximately 20-30 minutes on a single processor desktop pc.

Table 1 Elastic and Strength Properties for IM7/977-2 Carbon/Epoxy Unidirectional Laminate used for Numerical Analysis.

E11 =	153.06	GPa		+S11 =	2861	MPa
E22 =	9.65	GPa		-S11 =	-1551	MPa
E33 =	9.65	GPa		+S22 =	75.8	MPa
Nu12 =	0.27			-S22 =	-298.5	MPa
Nu13 =	0.27			+S33 =	75.8	MPa
Nu23 =	0.41			-S33 =	-298.5	MPa
G12 =	5.31	GPa		S12 =	102	MPa
G13 =	5.31	GPa		S13 =	102	MPa
G23 =	3.42	GPa		S23 =	52.6	MPa

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL DATA

Figure 4 presents experimentally and analytically generated biaxial failure envelopes for the unidirectional IM7/977-2 laminates tested. The 1/0 and 0/1 data sets demonstrated close grouping of the three specimens and are in-line with reported uniaxial strengths. Furthermore, the data points for each of the remaining nine biaxial stress ratios showed agreement with both their respective specimen and the analytical predictions granting great confidence in the validity of the experimental results. The four points in the upper right region of the tension/tension quadrant (encompassed by the brown oval) represent the final fiber failure strengths and the ultimate matrix strengths of the 1/1 and 5/1 specimens. It is important to note that those plotted biaxial strengths were not simultaneously applied to a coupon and the ultimate x-direction stress are mere approximates for the reasons discussed in the EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES section of this paper. The black boxes in Figure 4 contain the portions of the failure envelop that were well characterized by this study. The load frame's control system limited the applied stress ratio to $\pm 5/\pm 1$, the roughly 40:1 difference between IM7/977-2's fiber and matrix tensile strengths and 20:1 compressive strength discrepancy caused the predicted failure envelop to extend well past the region that could be experimentally demonstrated particularly in quadrants I and II. Since $-S22$ is close to four times the value of $+S22$, this test series was able to define a greater portion of the envelop in the quadrants III and IV of Figure 4.

Both the Helius:Laminate and Helius:FEA analytical failure envelopes correlate well to the experimental envelope. The experimental and numerical laminate envelopes predict nearly rectangular maximum stress behavior, as is expected with carbon/epoxy materials.

Figure 4 MCT Biaxial Failure Prediction of Unidirectional Unidirectional IM7/977-2 Carbon/Epoxy Lamina.

DISCUSSION

Overall, the FEA analytical predictions show good correlation with the experimental failure envelope for most of the two-dimensional stress space and only have minor deficiencies at some extreme loading conditions. Both numerical methods used in the present study offer significantly different approaches to numerically approximating the true phenomenon being generated in the experimental test and both should be considered differently. In general, the Helius:Laminate approach and results are in very good agreement with experimental data and almost exclusively a conservative prediction in all of two-dimensional stress space. Additionally, the differences between the Helius:Laminate approach and the experimental data are generally less than 10% for all load ratio conditions. It has been the experience of the authors that this level of correlation is rarely experienced with biaxial testing data. The significance of the predictions presented by this approach should not be understated as it represents the most complete biaxial data set and most accurate predictions for this laminate configuration available in the literature. Both will allow composites engineers to design more confidently. The authors attribute this close correlation to the decade-long development of MCT technologies, but also to a very precise material input data for this material system generated by the authors in previous studies [8]. Without accurate material input properties, accurate failure predictions would simply not be realized.

The analysis performed using Helius:Laminate in all regions of Figure 4 does a more faithful representation of the experimental data than does the Helius:MCT approach. This is a non-intuitive result as the computational effort required to perform the Helius:MCT approach is considerably more involved. While the exact reason for the numerical differences is not known, a closer inspection of the intricacies of MCT analysis offers some clues.

In the finite element method, numerical methods sample stress, strain, and material values at Gauss quadrature points. MCT failure analyses store a state variable corresponding to composite material damage at each of these Gauss points. Three composite material conditions or states, listed in increasing damage severity, are defined as: 1) Undamaged composite, 2) Composite damaged by matrix failure, and 3) Composite damaged by fiber failure. When either constituent fails, all its moduli are immediately reduced at that Gauss point. Since all constituent properties, both intact and failed, are known a priori, the micromechanics model is used to determine two additional sets of composite properties, corresponding to damage states 2 and 3, before conducting a MCT failure analysis.

The Helius:MCT analytical ultimate failure prediction of Figure 4 is underestimated in the σ_x direction by 15% when loaded in uniaxial tension, and 19% underestimated when loaded in uniaxial compression. These premature failure predictions are caused by failure propagation starting from the stress concentration near the arm taper shown in Figure 5. As shown in Figure 5 (1/0 load case), damage in the cruciform model generally began as matrix failure in the fillet that transitions the thicker loading arm into a gage region, proliferated to the radius section between the loading arms and ultimately progressed into catastrophic failure of the fiber constituent. This effectively reduces the size of the gage section, causing failure prematurely in the numerical specimen. Although this concentration likely exists and causes a local failure in the actual experiment, a localized stress relief most likely occurs in the form of a fiber pull out failure, mitigating the propagation that is not captured in the model. Additional evidence for this phenomenon can be found by considering any loading along the σ_y axial produces matrix failure in the gage section, which is not affected by fiber pull out. The analytical predictions along any load path dominated by a σ_y component provide excellent correlation with the experimental data. The authors theorize that the inclusion of an orthotropic degradation model for the fibers, rather than the isotropic model currently used, may better capture the stress relief. Future work will investigate this theory.

Figure 5 Stress Distribution of a Helius:MCT Specimen Resulting from a 1/0 Stress Ratio Loading.

It is also worth noting that the stress distribution presented in Figure 5 indicates that very uniform gage section loading is being achieved using the current specimen configuration. It is believed that the evolution of the current thickness-tapered cruciform specimen design allows for the generation of very consistent experimental data and advocates strongly for the ability of a thickness-tapered to perform accurate biaxial testing of many laminate configurations.

CONCLUSIONS

The authors have presented an analytical and experimental analysis of biaxial loading of an IM7 carbon fiber/977-2 epoxy matrix, unidirectional composite laminate. The experimental results were generated using thickness-tapered cruciform specimens on a triaxial material test facility located at the Air Force Research Laboratory at Kirkland Air Force Base. The numerical predictions were generated using classic strain decomposition technique known as Multicontinuum Theory and an associated constituent based, stress-interactive, quadratic failure criteria. A geometrically representative finite element model as well as a single element model was employed using MCT to generate multiple numerical predictions for this particular laminate configuration. Correlation between experimentally and analytically generated results varied depending on the specific numerical model used, exposing the paramount requirement for accurate input material properties when using advanced composite analysis techniques, as well as the general difficulties encountered when predicting the failure of composite materials. The authors provide discussion regarding several possible explanations for the discrepancy between experimental data and numerical models and offered insight into material behavior and accurate predictive techniques that could be pursued. Several aspects of the current procedures that should be reconsidered in future efforts to generate more accurate results were also discussed.

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